

Influence of Size, Shape and Charge of Organic Ions in Cation Exchange : Exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{H-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -Bentonite by Tetraalkylammonium, Alkanediammonium and Surface Active Ions

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The displacement of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{H-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -bentonite has been carried out by several tetraalkylammonium, alkanediammonium and long chain surface active ions at different concentrations. In general, the exchangeability of the organic ions increases with the size of the ions. However, with the tetraalkylammonium ions at higher concentrations the effectiveness of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ release from the clay matrix is inversely related to their size. The comparatively smaller tetramethyl ammonium and propane diammonium ions release greater amount of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from bentonite complex than the larger cetyl trimethyl ammonium or cetyl pyridinium ions. The selectivity coefficients of the long chain surfactants are higher than the other organic ions. The results have been interpreted in the light of the size and shape of the organic ions vis-a-vis the extent of van der Waals contact with the clay surface, and the space requirement of the large ions in the clay interlayer.

STUDIES on the interaction of alkylammonium ions and quaternary ammonium ions with montmorillonite have long been a fascinating field of research. Many interesting points on adsorption mechanism and forces involved have been revealed as a result of these studies. It has been observed that the affinity of the alkylammonium ions for montmorillonite increases in a regular manner with an increase in molecular weight¹⁻⁵. Usually, this affinity enhancement with molecular size has been interpreted only in terms of an increasing contribution of van der Waals forces to the adsorption energy¹⁻⁴. However, it has been shown recently by Maes *et al*⁶ that the free energy changes for the displacement of Na^+ in montmorillonite by various alkylammonium ions show better correlation with the amine gas phase basicities relating to the gas phase reaction, rather than with their molecular weights. This would suggest that the solvent screening effect is less operative in the clay interlayer space and the extent of hydration of the alkylammonium ions is lowered upon adsorption^{6,7}. So, due to the changes in hydration and van der Waals forces, the clay interlayer acts as an ideal medium for forming thermodynamically more stable alkylammonium complexes. It has also been noted that the adsorption strength of the alkylammonium ions increases with the charge density of montmorillonite⁸. All these information clearly indicate that the decrease of ΔG° with chain length of the alkylammonium ions should be considered to result from the combined variation of all possible factors at the clay surface and can not be ascribed

exclusively to van der Waals interactions as suggested by earlier workers.

Keeping these in view, the present study was initiated to determine the effects of tetraalkylammonium ions, long chain surface active ions and alkane diammonium ions of varying size and shape on the exchange behaviour of *tris*-trimethylene diamine $\text{Co}(\text{III})$, $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$, from its saturated complex with H-bentonite.

Experimental

The bentonite came from Evans Medical Ltd., England and $< 2.0 \mu\text{m}$ particles were used in the present study. The preparation of H-clay and the experimental methods for studying sorption of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ onto H-bentonite and its subsequent desorption by the organic ions are similar to those reported earlier⁷. The cation exchange capacity (cec) of H-bentonite was found to be 95 me/100 g by titration with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in presence of 1M BaCl_2 solution. The percentage (w/v) of $\text{H-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -bentonite suspension used for desorption studies was 1.638. The concentration of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ in solution was determined by using a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The maximum exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ onto H-bentonite corresponds to 93 me/100 g and compares well with the cec of the mineral which is 95 me/100 g. The exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{H-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -bentonite by tetraalkylammonium ions are

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{H-Co}(\text{tn})_-$ bentonite by tetraalkylammonium ions.

shown in Fig. 1. The isotherms are of the L-type indicative of strong adsorbate-adsorbent interactions⁹. The effectiveness of these ions as desorbing agents increases with formula weight at lower concentration of the ions while the situation is just the reverse at higher concentrations. The initial rise in the isotherms may be attributed to the increased contribution to the van der Waals forces to the adsorption energy with the size of the ions⁹ and to the changes in hydration states of the ions^{5,6} in the clay interlayer. However, as the exchange of tetraalkylammonium ions increases, there is an overall collapse of the interlayer space¹⁰ and as a result the replacement of the remaining $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ ions entrapped in the clay interlayer becomes very difficult by the large organic ions. Due to this contraction, further diffusion of the tetraalkylammonium ions into the interlayer space for the exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ becomes progressively difficult as the size of the organic ions increases. The area occupied by $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^+$, $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{N}^+$ and $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{N}^+$ onto clay surface are (31.0\AA^2) , (45\AA^2) , (77.0\AA^2) and (110.0\AA^2) , respectively¹⁰. Thus there is nearly a four fold difference in ion size between $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ and $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{N}^+$. Therefore at a particular level of exchange $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{N}^+$ or $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{N}^+$ ions occupy much larger interlayer volume compared to $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ and consequently further exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ is more hindered with larger $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{N}^+$ or $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{N}^+$. Accordingly, the percentages of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ release from the clay matrix by these ions are about 81, 70, 53 and 45 for $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}^+$, $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{N}^+$ and $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{N}^+$, respectively.

Fig. 2 shows the release of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from the clay matrix by decyl trimethylammonium (DTA), dodecyl trimethyl ammonium (DDTA), cetyl trimethyl ammonium (CTA), cetyl pyridinium (CP), ethane diammonium (EDA), $\text{H}_3\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{N}^+\text{H}_3$, and 1,3-propane diammonium (PrDA), $\text{H}_3\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{N}^+\text{H}_3$ ions. The isotherms show that the exchangeability of the ions increases with their size. As in the case of tetraalkylammonium ions, this behaviour may also be attributed to the increased

contribution of van der Waals forces to adsorption energy⁹ as well as changes in the hydration characteristics of the ions^{5,6}. Such exchange behaviour would be expected for a flat orientation of the ions at the clay surface as van der Waals type of interactions are additive and, therefore, would increase with the size of the interacting species. It is, however, interesting to note that all the exchange isotherms are of the L-type except that with PrDA which may be placed in the class 'C' in the classification of isotherms of Giles *et al.*⁹. This type of curve was also observed by Greenland *et al.*¹¹ in adsorption studies of amino acids and peptides from water on Ca-montmorillonite. The C-type represents constant partition between solution and surface, suggesting that new sites become available as solute is taken up by the microporous substrate and adsorption is always directly proportional to solution concentration.

It can also be observed that the extent of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ release from the clay matrix is higher with comparatively smaller $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ or $\text{H}_3\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{N}^+\text{H}_3$ ions than with the larger CP^+ or CTA^+ . This may be explained from the covering up effect of some of the exchange sites by the larger surface active ions lying flat onto the surface¹² and consequently a fraction of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ initially adsorbed onto the clay remaining unavailable for exchange. Further, among the surfactants the relative exchanging efficiency $\text{DTA} < \text{DDTA} < \text{CTA} < \text{CP}$ may be related to their decreasing critical micelle concentration (cmc) values which are 7.0×10^{-3} , 1.5×10^{-3} , 1.0×10^{-3} and $8.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$, respectively.

In order to have a better quantitative idea about the relative affinities of the desorbing ions at different concentrations of the electrolytes, the exchange data have been expressed in terms of distribution and selectivity coefficients and are recorded in Table 1. The distribution coefficients have been calculated according to the equation $\lambda_i = \frac{\bar{m}_i}{m_i}$, where \bar{m}_i and m_i are the molal concentra-

contact with the clay surface² and hence the adsorption energy is less than that for the long straight chain CTA⁺ or CP⁺ ions which are in close contact with the surface. Consequently, for the straight chain larger organic ions the size is more important than the charge in determining their selectivity for the clay surface² because the dispersion forces increase significantly with the length of the carbon chain. Moreover, as the size of the organic cations increases the solubility of the organic ion decreases in water and as a result there is also a less tendency for the larger ions, once adsorbed, to go back into the solution^{1,4}.

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